

SUSTAINABLE BIODEGRADABLE COMPOSITES FOR A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

Industries are working to reduce their dependence on petroleum-derived polymers, substituting them with biobased, sustainable, and sustainable alternatives in response to the climate crisis produced by gases. Agricultural waste generates huge amounts of lignocellulosic biomass, a sustainable resource for the development of various bioproducts. Bioplastics, which are made from renewable or recycled natural materials, can help make plastic use more sustainable by supporting a circular economy. Biocomposites, consisting of a bioplastic matrix and reinforcing fibers, have developed as unique materials with diverse applications serving as alternatives to conventional composite materials. Due to their biodegradability, bioplastics have attracted a lot of interest from a variety of industries, despite being a little expensive. Consequently, a number of methods have been put out to broaden their industrial uses. Some of them are blending with other polymers, using green additives, and adding inexpensive fillers to manage the production cost. A special kind of bio-based polymer made by microbes is called a bacterial polyester. For instance, PHAs are a natural polyester that may be produced enzymatically in vivo by microbes for intracellular storage. Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) is an aliphatic polyester and is a highly desirable bioplastic due to its marine biodegradable and home-compostable nature. PHBV is widely used to make rigid packaging items. Therefore, to achieve that, biocomposites were developed by melt-blending PHBV with natural fiber are becoming very popular. Some additives like peroxides, maleic anhydride-grafted polymer, a compatibilizer, are added to the formulation to enhance the interaction between the polymer matrix and the filler. To maintain proper melt flow for injection molding applications and increase flexibility, plasticizers are added. Adding a high content of natural filler will also help in improving the biodegradability of the materials, thereby adhering to the circular economy principles.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymers have a wide range of material characteristics, including hydrophilic or hydrophobic, flexible or stiff, and permeable or impermeable. The structure of the repeating monomers, which are the building blocks of polymers, controls these properties. After undergoing processing—usually involving heat—to take on a specific shape, polymeric materials are commonly known as plastics in their final, usable form.[1] These materials are extensively used and play a vital role in everyday life, particularly in industries related to transportation, food, healthcare, and energy. Plastics are now an essential component of human life due to their many desirable qualities, which have resulted in an increase in production volumes. Unfortunately, plastic trash has kept on accumulating and is posing a threat to our

ecosystem because production and use were initially planned for a linear economy (use and throw) and single-use, short-term applications. Utilizing plastics derived from petrochemicals has led to an increase in plastic trash, which is harmful to the environment and ends up in landfills, the ocean, and other habitats. By their very nature, discarded plastics remain unaltered for decades or even centuries, leading to the buildup of plastic garbage. If the plastic disintegrates, even then, fragmented micro- and nanoparticles are produced, which are harmful to the environment. Sadly, these particles have a detrimental effect on human health, especially when ingested, which exacerbates the threat of microplastics.[2,3]

Although plastics have improved our lives significantly and made society sustainable only during their use phase, new plastic materials need to be designed and developed following the circular (bio)economy (CE) principles.[4] In 1962, the European Union introduced the concept of which includes a variety of managerial, technological, economic, and quality assessment practices, with the assistance of numerous national governments, including those in China, Japan, the United Kingdom, France, Canada, the Netherlands, Scotland, Sweden, Germany, Finland, and other countries.[5] The CE definition has been interpreted in about as many different ways as there are circular economy practitioners and scholars, as explained by Kirchherr et al.[6] The requirement to use resources more effectively is arguably the only thing that all definitions have in common; however, it is still up for debate what exactly qualifies as "better." [7]

Nonetheless, it is evident that while waste mountains and related pollution are still accumulating, the world's natural resource depletion and related carbon emissions are increasing. For this reason, it makes sense that a circular economy would aim to minimize resource exploitation and maximize waste prevention.[7,8] A circular economy is being implemented by governments worldwide, including the EU, China, Tokyo, New York, and London, as well as through transnational initiatives.[9] A third of CEOs worldwide stated in 2013 that they were actively interested in the circular economy due to their own values, commercial objectives, and sustainability considerations.[7] The "CE100" program from the Ellen MacArthur Foundation provides businesses with a supportive atmosphere for learning and implementing circular practices.[7] Global leaders actively implementing a practice-based circular economy approach include companies such as Coca-Cola, Apple, and Rolls-Royce.[9]

The circular economy (CE) model, when applied to polymers, emphasizes maximizing the utility and lifespan of polymeric materials by reducing waste generation, having better end-of-life options, and promoting the reuse, recycling, and regeneration of plastic products. This approach transforms the traditional linear lifecycle of polymers (from production—use—disposal) into a closed-loop system, where materials are cycled back into their original state, supporting both environmental sustainability and economic efficiency. However, the concept of sustainability points out that every element of social and economic institutions should actively advance environmental preservation and economic growth simultaneously.[10]

Canada, along with multiple countries, is creating new laws and regulations to transition towards a plastic-free economy.[11] Single-use packaging is a significant source of pollution, making up around 46% of global plastic waste; fixing this issue will significantly lower the amount of plastic garbage produced. [12] Thus, it is clear that there is widespread interest in discovering practical equivalent packaging options that are also sustainable. While recycling plays a role in managing plastic waste, it contributes to just about 6% of the total plastic recovered, as a result, a significant portion of plastic continues to accumulate in landfills.[13] As such, using biobased and biodegradable polymers in conjunction with recycled polymers can be seen as an effective strategy to help reduce our reliance on petro-based plastics and minimize CO₂ emissions.[14]

Bioplastics are a class of materials that can be made from renewable sources. Therefore, materials made by biological processes, biobased materials, biodegradable materials, or a mix of these are often referred to as bioplastics. In this case, the building blocks (monomers) are obtained or synthesized from biomass, like plant-derived sugars, and then polymerized to create plastics that have properties similar to traditional ones or introduce new functionalities. Globally, around 2.5 million tonnes of bioplastics are produced annually. They are looked upon as essential to building a circular economy and addressing key United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. This includes reducing dependence on fossil fuels, creating new recycling or degradation pathways, and lowering the use of harmful chemicals during production. Moreover, bioplastics also offer benefits such as reduced carbon emissions, potential

biodegradability at end-of-life, and equivalent performance in certain applications compared to petro-derived chemicals.[1]

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs), a type of bacterial polyester, are amongst the most commonly used bio-based polymers, which are completely biodegradable in soil and marine settings and may be produced by a wide range of microorganisms under growth-limited circumstances. Because of their biodegradability, they are a viable alternative to popular petroleum-based polymers, including polypropylene (PP) and polyethylene (PE). They are particularly used in many single-use applications, like rigid packaging and flatware.[15] However, the production of PHAs is very expensive, which can be a limiting factor for their widespread use. PHAs are currently made by fermenting sugars and fatty acids that are obtained from food crops such as vegetable oil, corn starch, and sugarcane. Over half of the production costs are related to the cost of the feedstock alone.[15] This can be addressed by using lignocellulosic biomass, which is abundant and inexpensive or free, as a source of carbon for the manufacture of PHA. According to reports, approximately 300 bacterial species (both Gram-positive and Gram-negative strains) may produce PHAs in extreme circumstances and both aerobic and anaerobic settings.[16]

PHBV, or poly(hydroxybutyrate-co-hydroxy valerate), a commonly used PHA, is drawing a lot of interest in the production of sustainable materials.[17] PHBV is a copolymer of 3-hydroxybutyrate and 3-hydroxyvalerate and can be synthesized effectively using *H. bluephagenesis*. [18] PHBV shows biodegradation in marine, home, and industrial environments.[19] To counter the expensive nature of PHBV, it is frequently mixed with low-cost filler materials to develop biocomposites. These fillers can further enhance biodegradability while improving polymer performance.[14]

Therefore, biocomposites are composite materials developed by mixing biodegradable polymer matrix and a natural filler or fiber. Biocomposites made from bioplastic and plant-derived fiber (natural/biofibre), are thought to be more environmentally friendly. These composites are known as "green composites." The primary benefits of biocomposites are their sustainability, complete degradation, and environmental friendliness; in other words, they are genuinely "green" in every way. They can be composted or disposed of easily at the end of their life cycle without harming the environment. Biocomposites have been effective as materials in numerous applications, including mass-produced consumer goods with limited lifespans, single-use goods, or brief use before being discarded sustainably. Green composites have a several-year functional life and can even be utilized indoors. [20,21] Biofiber can have a reinforcing effect on the biocomposite matrix; however, it depends on many factors. The overall properties of fibres are largely influenced by factors such as their chemical composition, structural defects, cell dimensions, microfibrillar angle, and internal structure.[21] Some of the most important biofibers used for biocomposite fabrication are Abaca, Bagasse, Bamboo, Banana, Broom root, Cantala, Caroa, China jute, Coir, Cotton, Curaua, Date palm, Flax, Hemp, etc. [20]

As a result, research on PHBV-based biocomposites has also been conducted during the past decades using different fillers and fibers and evaluating the fiber performance on material properties. In some of the studies, Singh et al.[22] developed PHBV/natural bamboo fiber-based biocomposites, while Vandi et al.[23] developed PHBV/wood fiber-based biocomposites and measured the effect of processing conditions on the mechanical performance; Berthet et al.[24] made biocomposites from PHBV/wheat straw fibres for rigid applications. In another study by Nath et al. [14] the authors developed PHBV biocomposites by adding cellulose fibers (20 and 25%) and then added a compatibilizer [MA-grafted PHBV (MA-g-PHBV)] to see the impact of compatibilization on the biocomposite. To enhance the melt flow during processing, a plasticized TBC was added, which enhanced the melt flow suitable for injection molding, along with improving the impact strength and flexibility. The MA-g-PHBV compatibilizer was incorporated for enhancing the matrix-fiber adhesion, resulting in enhanced properties. During melt blending, a compatibilizer can be introduced to the composite to improve the matrix-fiber interaction. The most popular method for creating natural fiber/filler composites is the use of functional polymers grafted with maleic anhydride (MA). By reacting with free hydroxyl groups on the surface of the CF, it forms covalent linkages within the composite, enhancing interfacial bonding.[25] This proceeding paper later briefly explains a few works on PHA-based biocomposites to develop a consistent and robust composite for different application.

Figure 1: (a) Potential recycling pathways for biodegradable plastics (b) Based on global production capacities reported for the year 2021. Adopted from Kalita et al. [4] Copyright 2023 Elsevier, Open Access (CC BY 4.0)

2 Development of Biocomposites

For biocomposite formulations to be successfully adopted in industry, they must be compatible with standard production equipment typically employed in the plastics sector. This allows for easy transition from laboratory to industry, cost effectiveness, and scalability. As a result, biocomposites should be processable using typical procedures such as injection moulding, compression moulding, melt extrusion, thermoforming, blown film extrusion, and blow moulding. These processes are commonly used to manufacture many commercial everyday plastic products, and allowing the novel biocomposites to be created using these techniques would significantly increase the possibility for integration into mainstream applications such as packaging, automotive, consumer goods, and others.

2.1 Melt Extrusion

In the plastics processing industry, extrusion is a continuous production method that is mostly widely used to create products having a predetermined cross-sectional profile. In the process, a substance is forced out, much how toothpaste is squeezed out of a tube. The method of plastic extrusion involves forcing melted polymer(s), frequently in the form of strands, through a die. During the extrusion process via the die, the melt assumes the shape of the die opening. [26]

The polymer in the hopper is transferred into the heated barrel via the feed throat and a rotating screw. The polymer is melted by the screw's shear and barrel heating before being forced past the filter screen, into the die, and ultimately out. The extrusion techniques' main mechanics are solid conveying, homogeneous melting or plasticating, and melt pumping. The screw controls feeding, compression, and metering, making it the most significant factor in determining an extruder's effectiveness. Twin-screw extrusion is one of the most widely used processing methods in both research and industrial settings for producing polymer blends and biocomposites. In this process, biopolymers are exposed to a combination of high shear forces and elevated temperatures generated by the rotating screws and external heaters. This not only melts the polymer but also ensures uniform dispersion of fillers within the molten matrix.

2.2 Injection Molding

Injection moulding is a popular and adaptable process for creating polymer mixtures and composites. Plastic materials are heated till they become molten and viscous. This molten polymer is then poured into a closed mould, which specifies the desired shape of the finished product. Once within the mould, the material is allowed to cool and harden before opening, and the developed piece is taken out. This technology enables the accurate and economical manufacturing of complicated forms with high detail. Injection moulding is particularly useful in large-scale production due to its cost-effectiveness, consistency, and capacity to make high-quality products on a large scale. Its accuracy and reproducibility make it a popular choice for creating complicated patterns and components in a variety of industries. [27–29]

2.3 Blown Film Extrusion

Blown film extrusion is increasingly being adapted to produce films from biodegradable polymers, moving away from traditional plastics. This technology is widely used in the packaging sector to produce thin films that are generally no more than 100 microns thick. The polymer is first melted using a single-screw extruder, and then air is fed through the centre of a circular die to inflate it into a tubular film bubble. As the bubble rises, it cools and flattens into a two-layer film with nip rollers before being coiled into rolls. Blown film extrusion is a highly flexible process that may produce anything from basic monolayer bags to complicated multilayer films like those used in food packaging. Coextrusion is used to make multilayer films, which are formed by combining two or more molten polymer streams. Advanced commercial systems may coextrude up to seven to eleven layers, giving us great control regarding film functionality and performance.[30,31]

3 End-of-Life (EoL) options for Biocomposites

To transition to completely circular materials, it's important to design materials with effective EoL management. Figure 1 shows some EoL pathways for bioplastics. Biodegradable polymers disintegrate under specified circumstances near the end of their life cycle. Compostable polymers, a category of biodegradable plastics, degrade in industrial composting facilities. Biodegradable and compostable polymers can be made from either fossil fuels or biological resources. Biocomposites are typically designed with EoL biodegradation in mind under various conditions, rather than with a focus on recyclability.

The process of biodegradation is the transformation of organic components into residual biomass and biogas by microorganisms (bacteria and fungi) that use plastic as a carbon source. Biodegradation can take place inside the biosphere because microorganisms play a critical part in the process.

More than 90 microorganisms—aerobes, anaerobes, photosynthetic bacteria, and archaeobacteria are responsible for degrading and catabolizing bioplastics. These bacteria are abundant in soil and compost.[32] There are five primary stages in the microbial breakdown of plastic wastes: colonisation, biodeterioration, biofragmentation, absorption, and mineralization. [33]

There are different environments for biodegradation apart from soil and compost like marine, landfill, and sewage sludge, where each environment has its specific conditions for degradation. Different organizations such as ASTM, and ISO have established specific standards to assess the biodegradability of bioplastics under different environmental conditions.

Standards for biodegradation testing

Aerobic biodegradation

- Marine biodegradation: ASTM D6691-17, ASTM D7473-12, ASTM D7991-15, ISO 18830-16
- Soil biodegradation: ASTM D5988-18, ISO 17556, ASTM D5526-18, and ISO 14855
- Compost biodegradation: ASTM D5338, ISO 14855, ISO 117088, EN 13432, ASTM D5929, ASTM D6400, AS 5810, and AS 4736

Anaerobic biodegradation

- Sewage sludge biodegradation: ASTM D5210-92 and ISO 14853

- Landfill biodegradation: ASTM D5526-18 and ASTM D7475-11

Biodegradable polymers are exposed to a mixture of decomposed components at elevated temperatures during the composting process. Industrial composting is carried out at 60 °C, and with a high relative humidity in presence of oxygen. Home composting operates under milder conditions compared to industrial composting, primarily due to the smaller volume of biodegradable materials at temperature around 28 °C. [34]

Degradation under marine conditions is distinguished by low temperature, high salinity, high pressure, low nutrient levels, and currents compared to soil and compost.[35] Seawater is an intricate mixture rich in inorganic ions. The salinity of seawater is affected by factors such as evaporation, precipitation, river discharge, and seawater currents. The offshore and estuary waters are typically below 30‰ salinity, while the ocean's surface salinity varies between 32‰ to 37‰. With pH values spanning between 8.0-8.5, seawater is weakly alkaline.[35] It has been found that small pH changes (< 1) can modify the composition of the bacterial population. Moreover, the concentration of dissolved oxygen in seawater is substantially lower than in soil, and both are influenced by temperature and linked to biological activities, such as the amount and variety of marine organisms.[19]

4 RESEARCH ON PHBV BASED BIOCOMPOSITES

PHBV based biocomposites are becoming increasingly popular as they are biodegradable under soil, marine, home, and industrial settings. Also, by making the PHBV biocomposites high filler, the high processing cost of the PHBV polymer can be counteracted and the biodegradation rate can also be increased.

With this idea in mind, Nath et al. [14] developed a PHBV, and cellulose fiber (CF) based biocomposites having different concentrations of CF (10, 20, and 25%). With high concentrations of filler, the melt flow becomes very less, which reduces its processability. As a result, a plasticizer, tributyl citrate (TBC) was added to make the melt flow suitable for injection molding. Also, since there is an incompatibility between fiber and matrix, a compatibilizer MA-g-PHBV, was added at different concentrations. Additionally, three different types of MA-g-PHBV, with variation in grafting percentage, were tested on the biocomposites to evaluate the effectiveness of grafting percentage on biocomposite performance. Different characterizations, like mechanical properties, thermal, and morphological analysis, were conducted to evaluate the samples. TBC addition to PHBV decreased tensile, flexural strength, and modulus due to weakened intermolecular bonding, whereas CF addition increased modulus. Incorporating MA-g-PHBV improved all mechanical characteristics, particularly at 7% loading, due to improved filler-matrix adhesion. The addition of TBC led to an improvement in both the elongation at break (EAB) and the impact resistance of PHBV. The EAB improved monotonously with higher compatibilizer content. However, the impact strength increased after CF addition, as incorporation of long fibers sometimes led to improvement in impact strength, but no change was observed after MA-g-PHBV addition. Scanning electron microscopy and atomic force microscopy also showed improved interfacial adhesion with fewer gaps, voids, and pull-out fibers after the addition of compatibilizers. The observation demonstrates that MA-g-PHBV incorporation results in enhanced matrix/fiber interaction. The thermal stability analysis showed that adding TBC and cellulose fibers lowered the onset degradation temperature (T_{onset}), indicating reduced thermal stability, but the maximum degradation temperature (T_{max}) remained mostly unaffected. Overall, the thermal stability exhibited by the biocomposites was sufficient to allow melt processing at 170 °C with no adverse effect. Additionally, it was reported that the addition of MA-g-PHBV, having the highest grafting percentage, proved to be the most promising compatibilizer showing the highest improvement. This can be attributed to the presence of more MA groups, which facilitate more bonding sites for the OH present in the CF. Figure 2 shows the atomic force microscopy images of compatibilized and uncompatibilized samples showing reduced gap at the matrix and less fiber pullouts.

In another study by Ahankari et al.[36], agro-residues such as maize straw (CS), soy stalk (SS), and wheat straw (WS) were effectively incorporated into PHBV, using the melt mixing process to create novel green composites. The effective use of agro-residues as a great substitute for wood and synthetic fibres was the main emphasis of this study. This is because they are not only renewable, biodegradable, and advantageous for the environment and technology, but they are also affordable, widely available,

and easily accessible. The authors examined the impact of these biomass fibres on PHBV's performance. Reinforcing PHBV with 30% agricultural byproducts increased its tensile and storage modulus by up to 255% and 305%, respectively. Additionally, the tensile and flexural moduli of PHBV composites were much greater than those of equivalent PP composites for identical quantities of (30%) biomass fibres. Wheat straw fibers treated with alkali showed approximately a 35% improvement in both elongation at break and impact strength in PHBV composites, while having minimal effect on tensile strength and modulus when compared to untreated fibers. DMA research showed that the PHBV-biomass interaction was better than PP. However, tensile and flexural strength decreased with 40% biomass fibres addition because of a greater probability of agglomeration development in the polymer matrix. The addition of stiff lignocellulosic fibres to PHBV and PP composites also decreased their notch impact strength.

Mazur et al.[37] in their study used injection molding to develop biodegradable composites made of PHBV reinforced with either 7.5% or 15% of wood fibres (WF) or basalt fibres (BF). While WF composites had a decrease in strength and impact characteristics, but exhibited an increase in Young's modulus values, BF reinforced composites showed improvements in all these attributes. Composites containing 15% of BF demonstrated a 74% improvement in Young's modulus and a 41% increase in impact strength when compared to the unmodified polymer. Scanning electron microscopy was used to analyze the morphological structure of the biocomposites in order to determine the fibres' distribution and interfacial adhesion. Furthermore, biodegradation experiments of the biocomposites were conducted in saline solution to investigate weight loss and mechanical characteristics. It was discovered that the presence of fibres influences the rate of water absorption, with the maximum rate recorded in composites containing 15% of WF. After the first and second weeks, mechanical characteristics fell by around 10%. These findings demonstrate that biodegradable PHBV-based composites, including natural fillers, may be utilised to create long-lasting products. Table 1 provides a summary of some of the work conducted on PHBV-based biocomposites. In another study by Nagarajan et al.[38], injection-molded biocomposites were developed using switchgrass as filler in a PHBV and PBAT (poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) blend (45%PHBV55%PBAT). The effect of incorporating switchgrass fibre at loading levels ranging from 20-40 wt% was examined. Due to poor fiber matrix adhesion, a compatibilizer poly diphenylmethane diisocyanate (pMDI) was added at different concentrations. It was found that the compatibilizer was effective in improving the mechanical properties of the biocomposites. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to analyse fracture surface morphology, which revealed increased fiber-matrix adhesion in compatibilized biocomposites. FTIR data revealed an interaction between the PHBV/PBAT combination and switchgrass fibres with the addition of pMDI.

Figure 2: (I) (a) Mechanical Properties of PHBV/cellulose fiber (CF) composites with and without compatibilizer (MA-g-PHBV; referred to as “C” in the figure) [14] and (b) Impact strength and heat deflection temperature (HDT) of PHBV toughened with PBAT (45%PHBV55%PBAT), using switchgrass (SG) as a filler and poly(diphenylmethane diisocyanate) (pMDI) as a compatibilizer [38] (figure prepared by the authors); (II) Atomic force microscopy image of PHBV and cellulose fiber composite to show improved fiber-matrix adhesion after compatibilizer addition (a) PHBV-TBC-25CF (b) PHBV-TBC-25CF-7C [14] [CF stands for cellulose fiber and C stands for compatibilizer (MA-g-PHBV)](image taken by authors)

Table 1: Summary of studies conducted on PHBV-based composites.

Polymer used	Filler or Fibers used	Additives	Results observed	Reference
PHBV	Bamboo Pulp Fiber	Boron Nitride and MA grafted PHBV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fibers increased crystallinity, strength, modulus, and impact resistance of PHBV composites, with slight elongation improvement at low loadings. MA-PHBV enhanced strength and stiffness through better fiber-matrix bonding but reduced toughness due to restricted fiber pullout. 	[39]
PHBV	Bamboo Fiber	Silane and rare-earth coupling agents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High-modulus fibers significantly improved tensile and flexural properties and thermal stability compared to low-modulus fibers. Surface modification with silane and rare-earth coupling agents enhanced fiber-matrix adhesion and further boosted mechanical performance. 	[40]

PHBV	Cellulose nanocrystals and aluminum oxide nanoparticles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adding up to 3 wt% CNC improved tensile strength, thermal stability, and crystallinity, though higher loadings caused nanoparticle agglomeration and reduced performance. • SEM showed nanoparticle clustering at higher concentrations, while DSC confirmed increased glass transition temperature and enthalpy of fusion with CNC. • CNC proved more effective than Al₂O₃ in enhancing PHBV's mechanical and thermal properties. 	[41]
PHBV	Human hair waste (HHW), sawdust (SD) and chitin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PHBV was compounded with HHW, SD, and chitin to reduce cost and valorize waste. • Tensile tests showed SD slightly improved strength, while HHW and chitin had no reinforcing effect. • Soil burial tests revealed enhanced biodegradation with fillers, with HHW composites showing the highest weight loss (~35%). 	[42]

5 CONCLUSION

Simply using renewable resources does not ensure sustainability. With advances in technology, bioplastics have the potential to help in the transition of many plastic-heavy sectors to a circular economy. Presently, bio-based replacements are now available for most fossil-based plastic applications. However, these alternatives are often produced in small numbers, at a higher cost, and do not always provide clear environmental benefits. In addition to typical first-generation biomass sources, agricultural waste and lignocellulosic biowastes are more readily available, sustainable, and inexpensive. To make these alternatives really practical, biorefinery technologies must become more efficient and comply with green chemistry principles, such as avoiding toxic chemicals and reducing energy consumption, in order to generate the essential monomer in a sustainable manner. While efforts to achieve environmental sustainability are increasing, financial sustainability remains a difficulty. The affordability of fossil fuels, which is driven by low oil prices, tight business margins, and government support, makes it difficult for bio-based producers to compete economically. Advanced research is paving the way for lower production cost of biodegradable plastic resins. Moreover, adding low-cost natural fillers and fibers to the matrix for making biocomposites can help tremendously in reducing the price of the overall product. And these materials should be biodegradable more effectively in natural conditions.

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